

Three D's of V.S. Naipaul : Displacement, Dislocation And Diaspora

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Abstract:

Migration was a common phenomenon in the twentieth century and India was not untouched by this. The modern Indian diaspora is one of the most important demographic dislocations of modern times. Writers like V.S. Naipaul, from the Indian diaspora, reflect the yearning and anxiety of many men and women who continue to feel marginalized and disadvantaged in the developed societies. Hence, the diasporas and their descendants experience displacement, fragmentation, marginalization and discontinuity in the alien countries. Sir Vidiadhar Suraj Prasad Naipaul, born in 1932, is a Nobel Laureate who is a descendant of indentured labourer from India.

Naipaul leaves behind a complex literary legacy. As an interpreter of cultures, civilizations and histories, Naipaul appears distinct and unique. He has been living in UK and writing about India and the memories connected with his own country. Hence, as a child, he had felt two worlds separated- the childhood world of remembered India and the more colonial world of Trinidad, where his paternal grandfather moved to, as indentured labourers. In this paper, I propose to focus on Naipaul's writings, preoccupied with the themes of dislocation and migration, exile and experiences and was in search for his moorings and charting new identities, but still longing for their roots, culture, identities and retain connections with their homeland in literary manifestations.

Key Words: Migration, Diaspora, Displacement, Dislocation.

Introduction:

The modern Indian diaspora – the huge migration from the sub-continent that began in the mid nineteenth century – is not merely one of the most important demographic dislocations of modern times, it now represents an important force in modern culture. The diaspora counts among its members some of the finest writers – V.S. Naipaul, Salman Rushdie and Amitav Gosh. The term 'diaspora' refers to movement, dispersal, the concept of exile and fragmentation. Robert Cohen describes diasporas as communities of people living together in one country. They acknowledge that the old country is buried deep in language, religion, Custom or folklore and has some claim on their loyalty and emotion. The member of a diaspora community has a

permanent link with the past migration history. Even the children born to migrant peoples are influenced by the past migration-history of their parents or grandparents. Diaspora literature thus, has a close relationship between the diaspora's community and the homeland that they have left.

Migration was a common phenomenon in the twentieth century. People moved for various reasons from the land of their birth and adopted different cultures, languages and traditions as their own 'diaspora' has multiple meanings in the present context. If on the one hand, it is symbolic of indentured labour of the late nineteenth and twentieth centuries, on the other, it is a force exodus of the millions of Jews under racist forces. If it implies dislocation, it also signifies renewal. It is laced with the anxiety of belonging and unbecoming. Today Indians constitute one of the largest immigrant groups with a sizeable population in different parts of the world. This type of Indian diaspora embarks on new journeys in search of bright future, desire for knowledge, leaving behind their historical roots in the British nexus of imperialism. Writers from the Indian diaspora reflect the yearning and anxiety of many men and women who continue to feel marginalized and disadvantaged in the developed societies. Subject to racial bias, treated as objects of ridicule because of their dress code, food habits, colour, language and the spoken English, writers tend to expose injustice and equity through their works. The transnational migration of engines during the colonial and post-colonial times resulted in what today constitutes the Indian Diaspora. It is a result of the indentureship during the colonial period. Hence, the diasporas and their descendants experience displacement, fragmentation, marginalization and discontinuity in the alien countries. For the diasporas in their living 'in-between', In their hyphenated identities is a painful dilemma. With the passage of time the diasporas, however try to adapt themselves to the dominant culture of the subject country.

Background:

Sir Vidiadhar Surajprasad Naipaul, a Noble Laureate born in 1932, descendant of indentured labour from India, belongs to the group of such an Indian diaspora in UK. He has been living there and writing about India and the memories connected with his own country. Although ever since V.S. Naipaul started his literary career as a writer, he is known as a literary luminary, yet he never ceased to be a controversial writer for his oracle. Perhaps one way to enter the Naipaulian world is through the diasporic consciousness. His writings have been deeply affected by two experiences - the psychic tremors of indenture, a kind of banishment from India and later his exilic existence in England. As an interpreter of cultures, civilization and histories, Naipaul appears distinct and unique. His writings occupy a significant position between culture and countries. He is a writer who live on the margins of two societies and cultures. Talking about the loss of his moorings, Naipaul writes, "Nearly all my adult life had been spent in countries where I was a stranger..." Hence as a child, he had felt two walls separated - the childhood world of remembered India and the more colonial world of Trinidad, where his paternal grandfather moved to, as indentured labour. As a homeless cosmopolitan of Indian origin with West Indian social heritage and British citizenship, Naipaul's literary career spans

over four decades, producing a huge corpus of writing that includes novels, short stories, non-fiction, travelogs, journalistic writings and others.

Vidiadhar Surajprasad Naipaul has carved a unique niche for himself in the diaspora literature. He belongs to the generation of intellectuals who faced problems, which resulted from the withdrawal of imperialism and then subsequent cultural anarchy. Therefore, Naipaul began to travel in 1960 and since then he has been a restless wanderer - revisiting the Caribbean, making many trips to India, traveling to Africa, America, Malaysia, Iran, Pakistan and Indonesia - looking for things to write about. V.S. Naipaul's literary career was a discovery of his own self - of the colonial who had grown up in the tiny, backward island of Trinidad, amidst an insular Indian community and then with the racially mixed population of Port of Spain, the man who had no clear past or affiliations and who had to figure out the world he had been thrown into while attempting to perceive the many strands that paid up his self. His work seems to be the result of his own multi layered experiences : the many deprivations of Trinidad, the painful wretchedness of India as, as an outsider in England. Naipaul is an epitomized diasporic writer. He is twice displaced from his ancestral homeland of India, first to Trinidad and Tobago and then to Britain. Naipaul was born in 1932 in the British colony of Trinidad into a diasporic community of Indian descent.

Analysis:

Most of the Naipaul's writings issues from the desire to understand his own position in the world. He has drawn enough curiosity, much controversy and hatred from the third world countries. Naipaul had an ambivalent personality and this was due to his encounters of the of the colonial history. For example, his Brahmin ancestry, migration of his ancestors to Trinidad, his upbringing in a British colony and among negro slaves, Caribbean history and British literary tradition and his experiences developed him into a rootless personality. The unique combination of circumstances which related him to three societies and yet left him with a deep sense of homelessness, undeniably play a predominant part in shaping his sensibility and determining his writing career. He was born into exile, separated from his racial and cultural roots, driven into another exile from the land of his birth, a third disposition awaited him in England, he was really and truly lost and then he set out to 'discover' himself through his work. The contradictions inherent in his background from the pivot of his work. Naipaul's diasporic writings is preoccupied with themes like dislocation and migration, displacement, exile homecoming. One can observe that in Naipaul 's writings, the protagonist was in search for his moorings and charting new identities but still longing for their roots, culture, identities and retained connections with their homeland in literary manifestations. In this respect, Naipaul's writings resembled Stuart Hall's theory of unfixed identity, Clifford's traveling theory and Homi Bhabha's theory of mimicry and hybridity. Naipaul experiences initial struggle and hardships when he is relocated to a new country. Diasporic sensibility addresses issues such as change, racism, alienation, loneliness, rootlessness, displacement, nostalgia, cultural change, racism, homelessness. Naipaul himself keeps a desire to have his own identity.

As Naipaul says, "I am the sum of my books. Each book is infinitely worked out, stands on what has gone before and grows out of it. I feel that at the state of my literary career, it could have been said that the last book contains all the others." (Two Worlds, 480). Through his writings, Naipaul is able to rediscover a connection between his unfamiliar past and present self understanding and knowledge. Naipaul has wandered the world for over 50 years, chronicling the views and faiths of ordinary people in more than 30 works of fiction and non-fiction. In the narrative structures of Naipaulian imagination, the memory of home becomes paramount in the narratives where home itself is but a memory. This sense of alienation is also the writer's sense of a new being, the artist's vision of a new reality and therein lies the Naipaulian knot, traveling everywhere, belonging nowhere. Hence, the significance of the writing of V.S. Naipaul, for the betrayal of history is the central philosophical concern of all his writings. They are all about a single journey: the writers and the writing becomes the writer's home despite all exilic explorations in history, literature, politics and the old and new realities of our existence. History and literature, like Siamese twins, our Naipaul's way of apprehending the world, and an enigma of survival.

His writings clearly reflects the Indian diasporic experience. Through the character of Mohun Biswas, in *A House for Mr Biswas*, Naipaul explores the experiences and challenges faced by individuals living in a diaspora. Born into an Indian family, he grows up in a colonial society of Trinidad where his cultural roots are marginalized. He yearns for a sense of connection to his ancestral homeland and his Indian Heritage, yet feels like an outsider in both Trinidadian and Indian communities. Mr Biswas's journey revolves around his quest for a physical house of his own. The novel also throws light on the challenges faced by Mr Biswas in negotiating his identity within a multicultural society. Mr Biswas's attempt to build and own a house is symbolic of his hunt for a better sense of belonging. The hero, Mr Biswas battles for convenience, completeness, request and roots. He represents for the independent man's aspiration for his own house. Naipaul himself has lost his way of life as an Indian and he was unable to get Trinidadian while living in West Indies or English in London.

In the writings of Naipaul the vast majority of the characters are living as an exile in the outsider land. They have changed their nations, however, it is hard to change the way of life. Nostalgia about the native country is a powerful element in diaspora literature. We find a powerful element of nostalgic memories about the motherland in the writings of Naipaul. As Tenjinder Kaur remarks: "There is a yearning for home, to go back to the lost origin and imaginary homelands are created for the fragmentary and partial memories of their homeland." Discrimination is an important part of diaspora because it is a largely the discrimination in the country of birth that forces them to seek refuge abroad. This opens new perspectives and modes of thinking for the individuals and diasporans. In an era of globalization, the diasporans have radically changed and they have given up their national identities and have cultivated a broad vision and outlook. Although Naipaul condemns his land of origin (India) as an area of darkness but whatever his diasporic condition, his sense of exile and alienation, he tried to seek replenishment by making symbolic returns to his origins and thus we have *A Wounded Civilization* and *A Million Mutilates Now*.

Naipaul's ancestors were brahmins of India but they joined the bandwagon of the indentured labourers to Trinidad with some hope of a better future. But social and political systems of Trinidad had compelled them to alter their social and religious rituals, as a result emotionally they felt desperate and rootless. Naipaul writes about the Indian diaspora in Trinidad and Tobago - about suffering - a crisis of identity. They had come in search of a better life and remained there as aliens only. This expatriate sensibility of Naipaul haunts him throughout his literary works. His ancestral heritage nourishes his literary works, India and Indians are part of parcel of his works. Even after years of separation, he could not break his connection with India. The land of his ancestors continued to appeal to him. India continued to attract Naipaul who keeps on making successive journeys to help define his 'self'. Naipaul is generally assumed to be a harsh critic of India but his criticism stems out from his love for India. It is difficult for Naipaul to accept India but it is even more difficult for him to disown his country. His words speak volumes about his dilemma in his Nobel Prize winning speech, when he says, that Nobel Prize was "a great tribute to both England my home, and India, The home of my ancestors." Naipaul is a product of Indian diaspora who wants to link himself to the civilization of his ancestors.

Review:

As Alastair Niven writes "Naipaul's disassociation from Trinidad and corresponding incapacity to find a spiritual home elsewhere has been the basis for almost all his writing." The examination and analysis of his reaction to Trinidad began only during the writing of *The Middle Passage*. In *The Middle Passage*, Naipaul emerges as a bitter critic of the society that had produced him. It is clear that during the years of childhood and early youth that Naipaul spent in Trinidad, his antagonism built up as an undefined rejection of the society he saw around him. "A dot on the map of the world," says Naipaul of this small Caribbean Island off the coast of Venezuela. This recurring phrase reflects the sense of the insignificance of a political and cultural backwater like Trinidad that pervades all Naipaul's writings. What are the factors in the history of Trinidad - social, cultural, racial - which can explain and account for the despair it seems to arouse in Naipaul every time he refers to it? Is Naipaul alone in his perception of West Indian futility and Trinidadian cultural anarchy? Trinidad is peopled by the refuse of the other colonies. Naipaul shows "that the whole history of Trinidad was to be regarded never as a place in itself, always as a part of some grand ulterior European fantasy" Naipaul sees them as fragmented societies that cannot sustain life as it is evolving in the modern world. They have cars and phones but they are culturally and intellectually starved societies. He had described the effects of British, French, Dutch colonialism on the history and culture of Caribbean. Naipaul describes the inhabitants of these islands as divided among them, suffering from insecurity and lacking in vision. Thus, the community he explores in *The Middle Passage* portrays failure, futility, isolation, disposition and rootlessness, moving inexorably towards a menacing void. In 1979, Naipaul recalled "Trinidad as was incomplete in every way. Everything was imported. Every book, every machine every idea came from abroad. I felt I was lost, very far away." It was in every way a "borrowed culture" - a society of "mimic men". This was the society Naipaul grew up in and the society which he rejected in unequivocal terms. But it is also the society which he

knows best and which feeds his imagination and to which he keeps going back into his writings, as he says : "I have grown out of Trinidad". It was in India that he recognized how conditioned he had been by the multi racial society of Trinidad. As an Indian and Trinidad, he belonged to a distinctive minority, and in England too, as a Trinidad Indian he retained a separate identity. In India, when he blended unremarked in the crowd , he found it deflating and perceived then how necessary a stimulus, the sense of difference had come to him. His denunciation of Trinidad and India is itself a manifestation of conditioning and consequence of slavery - The unconscious acceptance of a typical European view of Third World inferiority.

Conclusion:

To conclude, one can say that his writing clearly reflects the Indian diasporic experience. Naipaul never treated India as his home, has had cultural and literary connections with India and the fact that he has written three books on India is a testimony to that fact. The reason for this is that Naipaul's diasporic identity has its continuous linkages with India - the land of his origin. Ironically, however, Naipaul finds himself doubly displaced - as a Brahmin, as an Indian immigrant writer. It is a paradoxical truth that he belongs to both and neither of the two. Thus, he is floating between two cultures and the two worlds. This is reflected in his writings which indicates his feelings of dislocation and displacement. Naipaul's situation throughout is that of one standing at an intersection, and therefore of dislocation and not belonging, every perspective he takes is immediately undermined by others and he suffers as an author and a man. He was a writer who encourages us continually to question, to write about the world with freedom of a person with no home, no country and no affiliations. The writer has shifting locations in globalized world, and hence it is necessary to understand the complexities of his dissemination. Thus, Naipaul's all literary art has been the fountain of inspiration of the diasporic vision.

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